

RESEARCH ARTICLE

“I felt there was no team to be included in”: Navigating social emotions and masculinities in engineering team projects

Vladislav Krivoshchekov¹ |
Marina Fiori²

¹École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Lausanne, Switzerland

²Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training (SFUVET), Renens, Switzerland

³Swiss Distance University of Applied Sciences (FFHS), Brig, Switzerland

Correspondence

Vladislav Krivoshchekov, Teaching Support Center (CAPE), École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Station 20, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland.
Email: vladislav.krivoshchekov@epfl.ch

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Abstract

Background: Engineering education often upholds masculinity norms such as individual competitiveness and emotional stoicism. These norms affect team dynamics and students' satisfaction with learning experiences in team projects.

Purpose: This study explores how social emotions experienced by computer science students, in conjunction with their (re)construction of masculinities, affect their satisfaction with learning experiences during team projects.

Method: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 34 students engaged in team projects at two Swiss technical universities. Each participant was interviewed twice: once at the beginning and once at the end of the project. We asked about their emotions, the reasons behind them, and their satisfaction with learning experiences during the project. Data were analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis.

Results: Two main themes were generated: (i) Hegemonic Masculinities describe patterns where students reinforced masculinity norms (i.e., competitiveness, prioritizing performance over social connections, and suppressing emotions to appear competent), which often led to decreased satisfaction with their learning experiences; (ii) Counterhegemonic Practices refer to instances where participants challenged these norms by promoting collaboration, sharing emotions, and providing mutual support. These practices enhanced satisfaction with learning experiences by fostering more inclusive and supportive team environments.

Conclusion: The findings highlight the role of social emotions in sustaining or challenging masculinity norms within engineering education. Suppressing emotions upholds the status quo and diminishes learning satisfaction, whereas embracing emotional authenticity promotes inclusive team dynamics and improves learning experiences.

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KEYWORDS

engineering education, learning experiences, masculinities, social emotions, team projects

1 | INTRODUCTION

Team projects are a cornerstone of engineering education (EE), equipping students with the technical and transversal skills (e.g., collaboration and communication) essential for their professional future (Van Den Beemt et al., 2020). While these projects foster problem solving, they also introduce complex social and emotional dynamics shaped by students' social identities such as gender, ethnicity, and/or sexuality. Existing research has highlighted that gender significantly influences students' roles, tasks, opportunities to voice opinions, and even the speech patterns considered acceptable in team contexts (Aeby et al., 2019; Meadows & Sekaquaptewa, 2011; Wolfe & Powell, 2009). However, the emotional dimensions of engineering project teams remain under-explored. Lönngren et al. (2020) examined epistemic emotions experienced in these teams, but there is limited understanding of how social emotions—those arising specifically from interactions with others—influence experiences in team projects (see Lönngren et al., 2024). Furthermore, EE research often treats gender as a stable, binary category, neglecting its nuanced interactions with emotional dynamics (e.g., Chen et al., 2023; Haines et al., 2001; Patrick et al., 2023; Secules, Sochacka, et al., 2021; Stump et al., 2011).

EE is typically characterized by rigor, competitiveness, emotional suppression, and individualism (Beddoes, 2024; Riley, 2017; Secules, Sochacka, et al., 2021). Such cultural expectations, understood in the current research through the concept of Masculinities Contest Culture (MCC), frame success as proving one's dominance and competence by embodying competitiveness and emotional toughness (Berdahl et al., 2018). Although research recognizes that masculinities—socially constructed meanings and practices linked to men's roles (for an overview, see Wong & Wang, 2022)—reinforce unequal gender relations by marginalizing non-conformity and prescribing specific emotional norms (Garr-Schultz et al., 2023; Messerschmidt, 2018), the relationship between MCC, social emotions, and students' team interactions remains largely unexplored. Initially, our data collection aimed at exploring social emotions within team settings. Yet, emergent themes distinctly highlighted the broader cultural context—best characterized by the concept of MCC—which shaped and was simultaneously shaped by students' social emotions, interactions, and practices in their teams. To our knowledge, this reciprocal relationship between MCC and social emotions in engineering team contexts has not been articulated in prior literature.

Given these gaps, this study builds upon existing scholarship emphasizing inclusive practices to enhance student learning (Habbal et al., 2024) by addressing the following question: How do social emotions experienced by computer science students, in interaction with masculinities, influence their satisfaction with learning experiences during team projects?

2 | BACKGROUND

2.1 | Masculinities in engineering education: Individual and structural dimensions

Masculinities are not inherent traits but a constellation of cultural and individual meanings attached to men and boys that are both learned and constructed and performed through social actions—a concept known as “doing gender” (West & Zimmerman, 1987; Wong & Wang, 2022). At the individual level, hegemonic masculinities are enacted when students perform assertiveness, dominance, and emotional suppression to legitimize unequal gender relations between women and men, femininity and masculinity, as well as among different masculinities (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; Messerschmidt, 2018). Individuals of any gender can perform masculinities and endorse masculinity norms, and minoritized individuals may adopt these norms to navigate male-dominated fields such as engineering, thereby perpetuating unequal gender relations (Derks et al., 2016; Seron et al., 2018). Conversely, counterhegemonic practices challenge entrenched norms and foster more egalitarian gender relations (see Messerschmidt, 2018).

At the structural level, EE fosters an MCC in which success is defined by continuously proving one's status through ruthless competitiveness, endurance, prioritization of work over personal life, and strict emotional restraint (Berdahl et al., 2018; Glick et al., 2018). In MCC, stereotypically masculine traits—such as emotional toughness, endurance, and

a “dog-eat-dog” mentality—become the standard, creating environments with omnipresent masculine defaults (Cheryan & Markus, 2020; Garr-Schultz et al., 2023; Henderson et al., 2023). This culture is evident in EE through practices and norms that emphasize individualism, discourage expression of negatively valenced emotions and vulnerability, and normalize competition (Cheryan et al., 2017; Godfrey & Parker, 2010; Schrock & Schwalbe, 2009; Secules, 2019; Tonso, 2006), creating physical and symbolic spaces in EE that marginalize non-normative identities (Riley, 2013). The “Sole Engineering Genius” identity, characterized by individualism—the belief that engineering expertise is sufficient to solve all problems (including gender inequality)—and intellectual superiority, further entrenches MCC (Lo Andersson & Landström, 2023). Further, diary data from female undergraduates show that EE successfully transforms potential critics of gender inequalities into agents of norms reproduction (Seron et al., 2018). Seron et al. (2018) highlight how female students internalize and embrace meritocratic ideologies, ultimately depoliticizing structural critiques and limiting calls for change, thus perpetuating existing masculinity norms.

The relationship between individual practices and EE norms is bidirectional. Engineering norms shape individual behaviors, and these behaviors, in turn, reinforce the MCC within EE. For example, when students devalue teammates' contributions in peer evaluations, they mirror and sustain existing norms that marginalize non-conformity (Dickerson et al., 2024). At the same time, these norms affect interpersonal dynamics; although social connections and friendships are vital in university settings, the pressure to maintain competitive advantages often discourages vulnerability, leading to isolation and hindering collaborative learning (Brooks, 2007; Scheidt et al., 2021; Vierra et al., 2023).

Moreover, masculinity norms are closely linked to sexist attitudes (Krivoshchekov et al., 2023a), violence against women (Krivoshchekov et al., 2023b), and increased risk of depression and suicidal thoughts (Eggenberger et al., 2024), contributing to discrimination, exclusion, and feelings of loneliness in EE at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels (Bahnon et al., 2022; Jensen & Cross, 2021). Women in engineering frequently encounter barriers, such as a lack of mentorship, which can deter their participation and retention (for a systematic review, see Cannaerts et al., 2025). Recognizing the pervasive influence of MCC underscores the need to address both the structural mechanisms and the emotional dynamics shaping students' learning experiences (Watzek et al., 2019).

2.2 | Social emotions in engineering team projects as a source of information

Team projects might become spaces where power imbalances occur, adversely affecting the learning experiences of marginalized group individuals (Aeby et al., 2019; Dickerson et al., 2024; Meadows & Sekaquaptewa, 2011). Understanding these dynamics requires examining social emotions—emotions that arise from interactions with others and influence social relationships (for a review of social emotions, see Hareli & Parkinson, 2008). To effectively capture the effects, we employ Tormey's (2021) three-dimensional model of social emotions, which includes emotions related to dominance and control (Status), trust and safety (Security), and belonging and affiliation (Warmth) (refer to the Results section for the participant-reported emotional terms associated with each dimension and for details on how MCC affects those emotional experiences in EE team projects).

Emotions also serve as social signals that influence team dynamics. According to the Emotions as Social Information (EASI) theory (van Kleef & Côté, 2022), expressing emotions clarifies social situations and facilitates interpersonal coordination. For example, a student expressing distress during a coding task may prompt supportive responses that enhance collaboration, while expressions of guilt or anger in competitive contexts can hinder cooperation and learning (Mänty et al., 2020; van Kleef & Côté, 2022). With the help of discreet emotions, observers can infer the social meaning of interactions without inquiry (Yeo & Ong, 2024).

Although Dickerson et al. (2024) used a different analytic lens, their study of peer evaluations in engineering teams can be interpreted through social emotions. Emotional labels such as “grumpy,” “inflexible,” or “perfect” encode judgments of Status, Security, and Warmth dimensions, subtly shaping students' social positioning within teams. These emotional expressions both reflect and reinforce normative expectations—particularly those aligned with masculinity norms in EE. Through the lens of EASI theory (van Kleef & Côté, 2022), emotional descriptors signal conformity or deviation from group norms, shaping participation and visibility in ways that often marginalize non-conformity.

Importantly, emotions are not neutral. Under contemporary postfeminist and neoliberal discourses (Benschop & Lewis, 2024), students—particularly those from marginalized groups—are encouraged to cultivate the “right” feelings of confidence, resilience, and positivity (Foor et al., 2007). Framing negative experiences as problems that require individual psychological adjustments diverts attention from structural issues and pressures students to suppress negatively valenced emotions such as disappointment or anger (Calder-Dawe et al., 2021). Such emotional work, often manifesting

as surface acting in team projects (Grandey, 2003), can lead to affective dissonance—a conflict between what students truly feel and what they believe they must display (Dobson & Kanai, 2019; Hemmings, 2012). Hemmings (2012) argues that making this tension visible—by voicing the frustrations that have been kept private—can turn individual discomfort into collective critique and change. In doing so, affective solidarity can motivate (majority group) individuals to advocate for change (Bleijenbergh, 2024), and overcome the individualization of inequalities (Ferry, 2024), thereby enhancing students' well-being and satisfaction in learning contexts (Supervía et al., 2023).

Finally, engineering curricula traditionally prioritize technical prowess and rigor (Riley, 2017), yet there is growing recognition of the need for transversal skills that include emotional competencies (de Lima et al., 2024; ENAEE, 2023; Isaac et al., 2023). Although various frameworks (e.g., the Inner Development Goals Framework; IDG Foundation, 2021) outline transversal skills as a goal, to our best knowledge, 3 T PLAY (Isaac & de Lima, 2024) is the only pedagogical framework of skill development with a direct focus on addressing and scaffolding engineering students' transversal skills. While aiming to equip students with essential interpersonal skills, the framework may not explicitly confront how masculinities shape team interactions in engineering team projects. Yet, students' capacity to “feel differently” may be key to challenging entrenched masculinity norms—a point we return to in the Discussion section.

3 | CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Our conceptual model (see Figures 1 and 2) integrates four theoretical lenses—performative masculinities (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; Messerschmidt, 2018; Wong & Wang, 2022), MCC (Berdahl et al., 2018), the three-dimensional model of social emotions (Oatley et al., 2006; Tormey, 2021), and emotions as social information (van Kleef & Côté, 2022)—to examine how social emotions enact masculinities to shape students' satisfaction with their learning experiences in engineering team projects.

We begin by situating social emotions within a three-dimensional social space (see Figure 1)—Status, Security, and Warmth—where individuals appraise their standing with respect to others and experience emotions accordingly (Oatley et al., 2006; Tormey, 2021). Status emotions (e.g., awe, anger) signal dominance or subordination; Security emotions (e.g., trust, anxiety) reflect perceptions of safety in the group; and Warmth emotions (e.g., compassion, happiness)

FIGURE 1 Social emotions and student satisfaction in engineering student team projects. In engineering team projects, students co-construct their social positions through emotional exchanges across three dimensions—Status (e.g., empowerment or dominance), Security (e.g., trust or anxiety), and Warmth (e.g., compassion or belonging). These social emotions act as informational signals that both reflect and shape how team members relate to one another. The balance and quality of these emotional interactions directly influence each student's satisfaction with their learning experience.

FIGURE 2 Macro-social shaping and micro-social co-construction of culture in engineering student team projects. This figure illustrates how social emotions experienced in engineering team projects mediate the enactment of hegemonic or counterhegemonic practices. Situated within a broader engineering and institutional culture shaped by Masculinity Contest Culture, students navigate “rules of the game”—such as individualism, self-sacrifice, and emotional restraint—through their emotional experiences. These experiences position students along the dimensions of Status, Safety, and Warmth, influencing interpersonal dynamics and team cohesion. Emotional practices—such as asserting dominance or showing vulnerability—translate into (counter) hegemonic practices, affecting satisfaction with learning experiences. The process is cyclical, as these practices either reinforce or challenge the wider culture of engineering education.

index belonging and care. Crucially, in an engineering team project, these appraisals and the accompanying emotions are not pre-given but are co-constructed through each interaction. Yet, team members do not enter on equal footing: a wider cultural context—one that shapes students’ dispositions, shared beliefs about valued behaviors, and “feeling rules” guiding how they ought to feel (Hochschild, 1979)—already influences their emotional repertoires from the start.

At the outset of our project, we had no a priori theory for how to characterize this cultural backdrop in EE. During inductive coding, however, we repeatedly encountered students describing why they felt anger, anxiety, or solidarity—that pointed unmistakably to a male-dominated engineering culture defined by individualism, contest, endurance, and emotional toughness. We therefore used an established concept of MCC (Berdahl et al., 2018) to capture this backdrop: a set of masculinity practices and norms in which behavioral patterns—individualism, competitiveness, prioritization of work over relations, emotional suppression—are associated with “being an engineer,” even though persons of any gender may perform them (Messerschmidt, 2018). Within EE, competing versions of what it means to be “masculine” are always at play, but one hegemonic account prevails, prescribing which emotions and practices are celebrated (i.e., “right”) and which are marginalized (i.e., “wrong”).

Nested within MCC, each team project is a social arena where students negotiate their identities by expressing or suppressing emotions in ways that can either reproduce or resist the masculinity culture. Informed by Messerschmidt (2018), we identified hegemonic masculinities in our data whenever participants narrated practices of competition, individualism, prioritization of work, emotional restraint, or assertion of status—broadly defined, practices that reward conformity to masculinity norms and legitimize unequal gender relations. In contrast, we interpreted as counterhegemonic those practices in which students vulnerably disclosed anxieties, preferred collaborative decision making, or deliberately fostered mutual support—practices that challenge MCC’s norms. Drawing on van Kleef and Côté (2022), we then understand these discrete emotional expressions not merely as individual experiences but as social signals: some affirm and reinforce status hierarchies (e.g., controlled anger as an assertion of dominance), while others signal a demand for more inclusive, egalitarian relations (e.g., empathy as a call for solidarity).

In sum, social emotions within engineering teams both enact and contest the wider MCC: the experienced emotions are shaped by the cultural feeling rules students bring into their teams, co-constructed in interaction, and ultimately feed back to influence individual satisfaction with learning experiences and the reproduction—or transformation—of engineering’s dominant culture (see Figure 2). By mapping these processes through the three-dimensional model of social emotions (Tormey, 2021) and the EASI lens (van Kleef & Côté, 2022), our model offers an analytical framework

for understanding how emotional dynamics can either sustain hegemonic masculinities or open pathways to greater inclusivity and equity in EE.

4 | METHODOLOGY

We adopted an interpretivist and constructivist paradigm (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015; Silverman, 2011) to explore how masculinities manifest in team projects through social emotions. Our primary research question, “How do social emotions experienced by computer science students, in interaction with the (re)construction of masculinities, influence their satisfaction with learning experiences during team projects?” guided the analytical process.

4.1 | Data collection

We conducted semi-structured interviews with 34 computer science students in EE as part of a larger project (for additional data from this project, see Kotluk et al., 2024). In line with appraisal theories of emotion (e.g., Scherer, 2005), our interview protocol (see Appendix A) included questions such as “How did you feel during teamwork?”, “Why did you experience those emotions?”, “Have you felt excluded?”, “Are you satisfied with the interactions within your team?”, and “How did those emotions affect your overall learning experience during the team/group project/discussion?”. Interviews were conducted twice (after week 1 in October 2023 and during/following the final week in December 2023) to capture temporal changes in emotions and perceptions. Interviews lasted between 45 and 60 min and were conducted in English (25 participants, N.K.), French (5 participants, Y.F.), or German (4 participants, E.W.). We ensured linguistic accommodation to enhance data credibility. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne.

4.2 | Participants

Participants were 34 engineering and computer science students from two Swiss technical universities, recruited via online flyers. Computer science team projects are a central part of the engineering curriculum and so were a natural vector for exploring their experiences in team projects. The participants represented two genders (11 identified as women (W), 23 as men (M), none as non-binary), diverse academic levels (from first-year bachelor's to second-year master's students), nationalities (including China, Switzerland, Morocco, Tunisia, Lebanon, Turkey, and France), and languages (first languages included Chinese, German, Arabic, French, and Turkish). English was the most spoken additional language, followed by French. This diversity provided a rich context of varied experiences. As gender is integral to our analysis, when quoting participants below, we use the pronouns corresponding to their self-identified gender. Table 1 provides demographic information about the participants. The details about their respective teams are not provided to reduce the risk of participants being identified.

University 1 is an internationally renowned technical university which educates around 13,000 students across a full range of engineering disciplines. An internal 2021 survey found that 81.2% of students agreed or strongly agreed that “I feel under pressure to perform and be productive,” while 47.4% of students (and 58.9% of teachers) agreed or strongly agreed that “I feel as though [this] is a place where people compete with one another.” Thirty students were recruited to take part in the research outside of their normal course work. They were financially compensated for their time in the project, and the project output was not graded. Seven teams were deliberately formed to maximize diversity in culture, language, and gender. Each team consisted of 4–5 members and was required to include at least one woman or one man, students speaking different languages, members from at least two countries, and at least one master's student or a final-year bachelor's student. They undertook a 6-week project to develop a language learning app featuring interfaces for speaking, listening, writing, and reading skills in languages other than English and French. Teams had full autonomy over their choice of languages, development approaches, and programming languages. Researchers observed weekly 2-h meetings without intervening. Participants could withdraw from the research at any time; consequently, one team was reduced to three members after a withdrawal in the second week.

University 2 is a university of applied science that offers blended (distance and onsite) Bachelor and Master programs with a practical orientation and has about 3000 students. Two teams were part of a computer science course and

TABLE 1 Participant demographics.

Participant (code)	Level of study	Self-identified gender	Country	Pre-degree	First language	Other languages (fluently)
P1M ^a	Master 2nd	Man	China	China	Chinese	English
P2W	Bach 3rd	Woman	China	China	Chinese	English
P3M	Bach 2nd	Man	Switzerland and Taiwan	Switzerland	Mandarin	French, English, German, Italian
P4M	Bach 1st	Man	Switzerland and Brazil	Switzerland	Portuguese	French, English
P5M	Bach 2nd	Man	Morocco	Morocco	Arabic	French, English, Spanish
P6W ^b	Master 2nd	Woman	China	China	Chinese	English, French, Korean
P7M	Bach 2nd	Man	Tunisia	Tunisia	Arabic	French, English
P8M	Bach 1st	Man	Turkey	Turkey	Turkish	French, English
P9M	Bach 1st	Man	Morocco	Morocco	Arabic	French, English
P10W	Bach 3rd	Woman	China	China	Chinese	English
P11M	Bach 2nd	Man	Tunisia	Tunisia	Arabic	French, English
P12W	Bach 2nd	Woman	Lebanon	Lebanon	Arabic	French, English
P13M	Bach 3rd	Man	Ghana	Ghana	Ghana-Akan	French, English, Spanish
P14W	Bach 2nd	Woman	France and Turkey	France	French	Turkish, English
P15M	Master 2nd	Man	Italy	Italy	Italian	English, French
P16W	Bach 1st	Woman	Tunisia	Tunisia	Arabic	French, English
P17M	Bach 2nd	Man	Tunisia	Tunisia	Arabic	French, English, German
P18M	Bach 1st	Man	Turkey	Turkey	Turkish	English, French
P19M	Master 1st	Man	China	China	Chinese	English
P20M	Bach 2nd	Man	Lebanon	Lebanon	Arabic	French, English
P21W	Master 1st	Woman	China	China	Chinese	English
P22M	Bach 2nd	Man	Morocco	Morocco	Arabic	French, English, Spanish
P23W	Bach 3rd	Woman	Lebanon	Lebanon	Arabic	French, English
P24M	Bach 2nd	Man	Vietnam	Vietnam	Vietnamese	English, French
P25M	Bach 2nd	Man	Lebanon	Lebanon	Arabic	French, English
P26W	Bach 2nd	Woman	Switzerland and Turkey	Switzerland	French	English, Turkish, German
P27W	Master 1st	Woman	Belgium and Morocco	Belgium	French	Arabic, English
P28W	Bach 2nd	Woman	Morocco	Spain	French	Spanish, Arabic, English
P29M	Master 2nd	Man	China	China	Chinese	English, German
P30M	Bach 2nd	Man	France and Lebanon	France and Lebanon	French	Arabic, English
P31M	Bach 1st	Man	Switzerland	Switzerland	German	English, French, Hungarian
P32M	Bach 1st	Man	Switzerland	Switzerland	German	English
P33M	Bach 2nd	Man	Switzerland	Switzerland	German	Italian, English, Russian
P34M	Bach 2nd	Man	Switzerland	Switzerland	German	French, English

^aParticipant-1 (P1); Man-(M) = P1M.^bParticipant-6 (P6); Woman-(W) = P6W.

were graded by their instructors. Since the team project was part of their coursework, they were not offered compensation for their time. Researchers did not participate in team formation or evaluation. Six students initially agreed to participate in the research; however, one member from each team withdrew during the process. Those who withdrew continued with the course as normal but did not participate in data collection. Teams met every 15 days for semester projects as part of their course requirements.

4.3 | Analytical strategy

We adopted reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) as our primary approach, which emphasizes the active role of researchers in constructing meaning and rejects positivistic interpretations (Braun & Clarke, 2019, 2021; Byrne, 2022). Initially, our research aimed to investigate social emotions and power relations broadly; however, early interviews revealed a predominant salience of masculinity dynamics. Consequently, before coding and analysis, we shifted our focus to examining how social emotions enact masculinities, as detailed in our conceptual model (refer to Section 3). We view ourselves not as detached observers but as integral participants in knowledge construction, aligning with post-humanist and post-qualitative perspectives (Lather & St. Pierre, 2013).

All interviews were transcribed verbatim in their original languages (English, French, or German) to preserve linguistic and emotional nuance using aTrain software (Haberl et al., 2024). Subsequently, non-English transcripts were translated into English and validated by the original interviewers to ensure both semantic and affective accuracy. Our analysis was structured around the interview questions, which explicitly probed for what provoked emotions in team interactions and how emotions affected learning experiences. The first author deepened data engagement through repeated readings, during which we iteratively highlighted segments—“features”—that were related to power, vulnerability, or emotional expression relevant to our research question (see Table 2). These “features” consistently included explicit student reports of emotions alongside detailed contextual explanations of what provoked those emotions and how they were regulated.

Using qualitative data analysis software, the first author conducted open coding iteratively, working through transcripts in several passes. In each pass, every excerpt was coded on two parallel axes: (a) its emotional content (Status, Security, Warmth) derived from our conceptual model, and (b) the team-interaction context that signified hegemonic or counterhegemonic practices. To explicitly map the connections between social emotions, (counter)hegemonic masculinities, and learning experiences, we used responses to the final interview questions (e.g., “How did those emotions affect your ability to contribute to discussions and your overall learning experience during the team project? Did those emotional experiences make it easier or harder for you to engage and learn?”). Participants' answers were open-coded to capture direct references to learning experiences, and these experience-related codes were subsequently linked to previously assigned emotion and masculinity codes within similar interaction contexts. To ensure transparency and reduce bias, the first author met weekly with two co-authors to review the codes, compare and validate interpretations, and update the evolving codebook. After this cycle of weekly checks, we held a full-team meeting (all authors) to reconcile outstanding discrepancies and confirm that each emotional excerpt was simultaneously linked to both its team context and the masculinity context. Throughout, the first author maintained a reflexive journal, and analytic memos were shared with collaborators to document how our positionalities shaped coding decisions.

Guided by Byrne (2022), themes emerged inductively as we grouped similar codes around central concepts. We then refined these themes by incorporating deductive elements that linked our findings to established theoretical frameworks and our conceptual model (refer to Section 3). Our final themes—encompassing both semantic and latent meanings—were iteratively reviewed and adjusted, ensuring they accurately represented the data and addressed the research question.

4.4 | Positionality

Throughout the research process, we remained mindful that our interpretation of the experiences is one of many possible. To this end, it is important to situate our experiences (Secules, McCall, et al., 2021). Our team brings together multilingual scholars from diverse disciplinary backgrounds—including physics, mathematics, sociology, psychology, and learning sciences—trained primarily within the Western intellectual tradition. While our individual research trajectories vary, they converge around shared interests in higher education, emotions, and social identity. Three of the

TABLE 2 Exemplars of comments, initial notes, and initial codes.

Initial notes taken during data familiarization	Data excerpts (participant quotes)	Example of initial codes during coding	Final code/sub-theme/theme
Participants often mentioned a situation where they felt frustrated with how things are happening.	“And that is of course frustrating, or because if you continue to make a contribution, you naturally want to be heard.” (P31M)	Frustration with being unheard. Desire for recognition. Effort to contribute but feeling ignored.	Frustration from team members' lack of recognition of contributions by others during teamwork/ Questioning Status-Quo/ Counterhegemonic Practices
	“I saw them all taking their computers, looking at it, doing some stuff. I was like, ‘What are they doing? Why am I not doing anything? Why do I not have the same thing they have?’ So maybe it's not just about the exercise; it's also about the fact that—uh—why, like, what are they doing? First of all, I was frustrated because I didn't understand. So not understanding, even in life in general, if I don't understand my course, it's something, but if I don't understand anything else, it's also something like—uh—frustrating for me in general. So I'd say the fact of not understanding, uh, and still like, I still had something to do, and uh, it wasn't clear exactly.” (P14W)	Lack of clarity in roles/tasks. Frustration due to misunderstanding. Desire for equal participation. Confusion and frustration over project direction. Sense of exclusion and isolation.	
Participants often mentioned that they cope with negative emotions through work.	“When I'm worried, I want to do my best to complete the task.” (P13M)	Using work to manage emotions. Negative emotions fueling productivity. Work as a coping mechanism.	Suppression of negative emotions through work/ Show No Weakness/ Hegemonic Masculinities
	“Stress fueled me, made me more aware of the situation, and allowed me to work more on the project.” (P11M)	Stress enhancing focus. Channeling negative emotions into work. Increased effort due to pressure.	

authors are currently based at the same technical university: one author addresses issues of masculinities within educational contexts, while two others have, over the past 5 years, investigated the role of emotions in EE. In addition to their research, these two also serve as learning scientists tasked with supporting and enhancing EE at the university: as part of their roles, they work closely with engineering students and instructors, engaging directly with the everyday realities of teaching and learning in engineering. Three other authors are based at different universities in Switzerland. Their work has illuminated how emotions shape learning, engagement, and identity formation in academic contexts, including—but not limited to—STEM education. Together, we bring complementary perspectives that allow us to examine the affective dimensions of EE from multiple points: as researchers, as educators, and as professionals embedded within the systems we study. This dual positioning—both as reflective scholars and as active participants—grounds our perspective at the intersection of theory and practice and enables us to engage critically and reflectively with the emotional dynamics of EE using both qualitative and quantitative methods, developing richer, nuanced interpretations.

5 | RESULTS

RTA of the interviews generated two overarching themes that were labeled hegemonic masculinities and counterhegemonic practices (see Figure 3, Table 3). Within these themes, several sub-themes emerged that illustrate the participants' experiences within their computer science team projects. As will be seen in the data presentation below, these sub-themes overlap and interpenetrate; they provide a way of describing different features of the overarching theme, rather than being distinct. Table 4 clarifies the emotional vocabulary used in these themes: it groups the emotional terms participants used under Status, Security, and Warmth and shows how each relates to MCC.

5.1 | Hegemonic masculinities

This theme encapsulates how patterns of practices associated with the positions of men within the heteronormative gender system (i.e., masculinities) are constructed, (re)produced, and maintained within the team projects. Participants often discussed competitive atmospheres, the prioritization of work over personal well-being, and the suppression of emotions to display an image of competence. Together, this theme illustrates how hegemonic masculinities are socially and emotionally constructed within EE contexts, perpetuating unequal gender relations and undermining collaborative learning.

5.1.1 | Competitive individualism

The competitive individualism sub-theme captures the pervasive sense of competition within team projects at University 1 mentioned above, reflecting an institutional culture that many feel prioritizes individual achievement over collaboration, also reinforced through team leadership practices that embody assertiveness and visibility. This environment aligns with the MCC, where success is often measured by outperforming others, fostering rivalry, and emphasizing personal recognition (Berdahl et al., 2018).

Participants internalized these expectations, frequently expressing emotions aligned with the Status dimension of social emotions, such as frustration or pride, linked to their perceived success or failure in outperforming peers.

Even if it's not great or whatever, if we can do it, we can do it like properly and some specific time and everything. And when I'm like with others, they just don't see it the same way. It can be frustrating. So I think that is why I felt that way. And we are always used here at [university] like even if something is not graded or whatever, we just have to do it well anyway.

(P27W)

While initially this may appear as a personal preference for quality, within the EE context—characterized by high standards, rigorous assessment, and ongoing comparison with peers—this sentiment reflects masculinity norms where individual excellence and superiority are integral to gaining recognition and status. This frustration reflects how status-oriented emotions emerge when expectations of excellence, deeply embedded within EE culture, are unmet, thus

FIGURE 3 Finalized thematic map demonstrating two themes.

TABLE 3 The final themes, definitions, and distinctive features.

Final themes	Final sub-themes	Short definition	Distinctive features	Core emotions
Hegemonic masculinities	Competitive Individualism	Culture of rivalry and personal achievement	Competitive atmosphere. Exclusionary practices. Leadership tied to assertiveness and visibility. Scarce trust. Status emphasis.	Anger Disappointment Pride
	Show No Weakness	A facade of confidence, suppression of negative emotions	Emotional suppression. Avoidance of vulnerability Stoicism. Work as coping mechanism. Facade of confidence.	Shame Anger/ Frustration Guilt
	Put Work First	Emphasizing productivity above well-being	Preference for solitary work. Suppression of social interactions. Valuing self-reliance. Overwork as value. Emotional needs secondary.	Worry Boredom Satisfaction
Counterhegemonic practices	Questioning the Status-Quo	Challenging hierarchy and rigid norms	Challenging norms. Advocating inclusivity. Desiring social interaction. Opposing hierarchical dynamics.	Frustration Hope Empathy
	Collaboration Over Competition	Prioritizing teamwork and collective success	Teamwork emphasis. Mutual support. Open communication. Inclusive leadership. Learning from others.	Satisfaction Admiration Joy
	Emotional Support	Embracing open emotional expression	Empathy and understanding. Emotional expression. Building trust. Adjusting actions. Challenging emotional suppression norm.	Trust Compassion Empathy

Note: Each main theme represents a broader set of gendered practices (either hegemonic or counterhegemonic), while each sub-theme captures a distinct aspect of these practices along with a concise definition and description of its distinctive features. For each sub-theme, we have highlighted three core emotions that were most prevalent in the interview data. Note that while these three emotions were selected to provide a focused snapshot, other emotional responses were identified and are discussed in greater detail in the Results section.

reinforcing masculinity practices rooted in competitive dominance, legitimizing hierarchies of competence, and marginalizing those unable or unwilling to meet these standards.

Competitive individualism also shaped exclusionary practices within teams, disproportionately impacting participants marginalized by gender or linguistic background. Participant 6, the only woman in her team, described being excluded from major decisions, highlighting gendered dynamics:

Oh, excluded. Yeah, the thing I told you, the Android changed to the Java app. I feel a bit excluded at that time. I was like, why no one tell me? And then they said, because we cannot do the Android app. And then I said, okay, fine. That is the only moment.

(P6W)

Her exclusion reflects the broader EE context, where women's competence or perspectives are frequently overlooked in male-dominated environments. She further noted how exclusionary practices occurred through informal men's interactions, reinforcing belonging among men but marginalization of women:

TABLE 4 Tormey's dimensions of social emotions and their interactions with Masculinity Context Culture (MCC).

Dimension	Representative emotional terms	Interaction with MCC
Status (dominance/ control)	Pride, triumph, confidence, anger, frustration, contempt, competitiveness, disappointment, shame, embarrassment, awe, guilt, admiration, satisfaction	MCC encourages high-arousal, assertive emotions (anger, triumph) that signal dominance and discourage challenge; it suppresses status-threat emotions such as shame or embarrassment by framing them as weakness.
Security (psychological safety/trust)	Trust, comfort, calmness, relief, vulnerability, fear, anxiety, uncertainty, worry	MCC stigmatizes open displays of vulnerability, fear or anxiety; students may privately feel insecure but publicly mask it, thereby eroding genuine trust and psychological safety.
Warmth (belonging/ affiliation)	Compassion, warmth, gratitude, empathy, kindness, hope, joy, sadness, loneliness, boredom, satisfaction	Warmth-oriented emotions are often devalued as “weak” or non-technical; MCC pressure to appear stoic dampens their expression.

Note: Some terms (e.g., competitiveness, vulnerability) are not classified as discrete emotions in usual taxonomies, yet we retain them to reflect participants' own phrasing. In our framework, we labeled emotions as “social” when the respondent tied it to a relational focus—another person, the team, or broader group dynamics. Because this social character depends on context rather than on the label itself, a single term may align with different dimensions in different situations.

Abbreviation: MCC, masculinity context culture.

They said, you guys always talk with each other and don't talk with me. Because all of them are men and they always, yo, bro, yo, bro. And they go to the toilets together. So, they also talk a lot, like everywhere, but they didn't tell me that.

(P6W)

Her emotional experience—alienation and exclusion—illustrates how the MCC in EE functions through informal interactions. Men's bonding reinforces masculinity norms by privileging Warmth selectively among men while actively denying such emotional connection to women, sustaining unequal gender relations. Additionally, linguistic barriers further reinforced Participant 6's experience of exclusion, amplifying her marginalization within the Security dimension, as emotional signals of belonging (conversations, laughter) were inaccessible to her, limiting her full participation:

So just like during the break, they go to the [men's] toilet together, and then doing the water together, and they talk and have fun. I cannot join them. ... They can speak really fluent French together. But actually my French is just the intermediate level. I can listen and understand what they say, but I cannot speak that fast and insert in the conversation.

(P6W)

A liminal zone emerged in which students neither fully acknowledged nor wholly dismissed experiences of social exclusion, signaling the routinization of competitive, emotionally detached norms. One participant explained, “I felt there was no team to be included in; everyone was in their own direction” (P22M), articulating a general sense of alienation. Another remarked, “I think it's a very common phenomenon here. So, it doesn't deserve some analysis” (P21W), framing exclusion as an unremarkable feature of the environment. Such comments illustrate how competitive individualism and emotional distancing have become normalized within EE culture: feelings of isolation are interpreted as inevitable rather than as indicators of a dysfunctional climate. This resigned acceptance implicitly affirms MCC, marginalizing students who seek relational engagement in learning and thereby diminishing the potential for inclusive practices to emerge and thus preserving the status quo.

Participants' interpretations of inclusion and exclusion further legitimized hierarchy based on perceived competence. Participant 11 defined inclusion narrowly through task allocation rather than genuine belonging:

It's not about like being excluded. It's that maybe certain members weren't as good in the programming, so they didn't contribute much to the coding but they contributed in their own way in like the aesthetic part and styles. So, like I said, some people may be excluded from one task or main task, but focused on another one.

(P11M)

This rationalization emphasizes functional inclusion, neglecting emotional aspects such as Security (trust) or Warmth (belonging), which are critical for true collaboration. Such practices legitimize hierarchies rooted in competitive individualism, indirectly sustaining unequal gender relations by marginalizing emotional needs often coded as feminine or weak within EE.

Peer benchmarking proved to be a potent trigger for status-oriented emotions, affecting both students' perceptions of competence and their learning experiences. Following a project showcase, one participant observed, "After having seen what the other groups have done, I think we could have added a learning part..." (P13M), while another noted, "I assumed we would finish it all that day. But it's still far from perfect" (P34M). These remarks reveal disappointment not as a collaborative impulse to refine the project but as a competitive, upward comparison signaling a perceived loss of standing. The emotional experience of falling short re-centered the task around restoring personal status—a reinforcement of MCC—rather than around collective knowledge building. In this way, status-oriented emotions redirected effort away from open problem solving toward individualized attempts to "catch up", thereby constraining the collaborative learning opportunities that team projects are intended to produce.

Leadership practices further reinforced masculinized status hierarchies. When asked about leadership—whether their teams had leaders and how these leaders emerged—participants typically described leadership as arising "naturally" through the demonstration of technical competence or assertiveness. Participant 19 explicitly linked his emergence as a team leader to his ability to visibly demonstrate expertise:

Yeah, naturally. Like, for example, for me, I just kind of mentioned that, okay, I have some expertise in software engineering. I show some of my expertise. And that's how it works [how I become a leader].
(P19M)

Participant 2 similarly described a teammate becoming recognized as a leader specifically due to his continuous assertive communication, making himself visible through repeated sharing of ideas:

He keeps talking; he keeps sharing his ideas, and we feel like, oh yeah, correct, reasonable. So, it's like following his ideas, and this makes him like a leader.
(P2W)

These responses illustrate how leadership roles were constructed through behaviors aligned with masculinity norms—particularly the emphasis on individual technical expertise, assertiveness, and consistent visibility. Consequently, leadership practices implicitly marginalized alternative forms of leadership that might prioritize emotional openness, collaborative decision making, or relational support, thus reinforcing the Status dimension and perpetuating unequal gender relations within the EE context.

Overall, the competitive individualism sub-theme highlights how competition, exclusion, and hierarchical leadership legitimize unequal gender relations within EE. Through emotions aligned with Status (pride, frustration, dissatisfaction), participants reinforce unequal gender relations, marginalizing emotional expressions emphasizing Security (trust, vulnerability) and Warmth (belonging, empathy). Such normalized and unquestioned dynamics not only reinforce inequalities between femininity and masculinity but also sustain hierarchies among different forms of masculinities, perpetuating structural exclusion and undermining collaborative learning, making it challenging to introduce inclusive practices that could enhance learning experiences for teams. By emphasizing individual success over collaboration, the focus on competition undermines the development of secure attachments and warmth—emotions such as trust, empathy, and belonging—essential components for satisfaction with learning experiences.

5.1.2 | Show no weakness

The Show No Weakness sub-theme captures an expectation to maintain a facade of confidence and composure within engineering teams, suppressing negatively or overtly positively valenced emotions to project competence and reliability, thereby reinforcing gender inequalities by legitimizing masculinities that equate emotional vulnerability with weakness or incompetence. This aligns with the MCC, where individuals are expected to display unwavering confidence and avoid any display of vulnerability—a notion often summarized as "no sissy stuff" (Glick et al., 2018).

Participants deliberately concealed their emotions to protect their professional image and avoid what they perceived as burdening others. Participant 30 described emotional suppression as respectful behavior:

I usually hide them [my emotions] ... Because I think that it's part of being respectful sometimes.

(P30M)

Rather than purely personal courtesy, Participant 30's practice reflects MCC expectations where emotional openness is marginalized, reinforcing a culture of masculinized self-control. His emotional suppression signals conformity to gendered expectations, marginalizing relational emotional expressions (Security, Warmth).

Participant 23 similarly suppressed negatively valenced emotions, explicitly to avoid burdening teammates:

Because I feel if I'm going to show negative emotions, it can be a burden to people. And I don't like to affect them.

(P23W)

Her concern reveals gendered pressures within EE culture: emotional openness (seen as feminine) is constructed as disruptive or burdensome, legitimizing masculinity norms that equate professionalism with stoicism. Participant 23's suppression indicates adherence to masculinity norms, perpetuating unequal gender relations by marginalizing relational emotional needs.

Many participants recognized negatively valenced emotions as threats to productivity, explicitly linking emotional control to competence. Participant 15 admitted emotional suppression was necessary for maintaining personal productivity:

The fact that I was annoyed... probably had a detrimental effect on my performance because I was too distracted by the fact that others weren't doing as much as I would have liked them to do and got distracted by that instead of focusing on doing what I had to do.

(P15M)

Participant 29 described how experiencing negatively valenced feelings led her to withdraw from active participation:

Yeah, I stayed there and I think I suggested less. I don't want to provide my suggestion for this project. I just like, okay, you name it, you say it. Okay, so I obey your rules.

(P29W)

These behaviors illustrate how suppressing negatively valenced emotions aligns with masculinity norms emphasizing individual control and emotional autonomy, sacrificing genuine emotional engagement (Security and Warmth dimensions). Participants' withdrawal from collaboration reinforces unequal gender relations by equating emotional suppression with professionalism, marginalizing open expressions of frustration, dissatisfaction, or vulnerability that could otherwise enhance collaborative problem solving and support.

Some female participants highlighted additional pressures to adhere to masculinity norms. Participant 27 noted the gendered stigma attached to emotional expression:

As a female engineer in the team, if you show your emotions, you will be considered as a bit more weak.

(P27W)

When asked if she prefers to hide negatively valenced emotions to avoid being judged as weak, Participant 2 affirmed, "Yes." (P2W).

These insights emphasize how emotional suppression functions as a gendered practice: students from marginalized groups are penalized for emotional openness, reinforcing masculinity norms where competence is inversely related to emotional vulnerability. Thus, emotional suppression directly legitimizes gender inequalities by pressuring women to conform to masculinity norms or risk diminished professional status.

Participants also moderated overtly positively valenced emotions to align with EE's masculinity “rational engineer” archetype. Participant 28 consciously limited her enthusiasm:

I just didn't want to be there but I had to stay because I can't make a decision based on a real quick impression, so I stayed and I tried to put on the best face... trying to be cordial and a bit friendly... when I'm interested, I'm really excited and sometimes it's not appropriate to be too excited... I just toned down and... being participative and trying to do the best I can in my task.

(P28W)

Participant 8 echoed this self-monitoring, remarking that even genuine happiness rarely moves beyond a “little smirk” (P8M). By moderating positively valenced affect, both students aligned themselves with masculinity norms that equate professionalism with measured detachment, thereby limiting opportunities for expressive engagement that might otherwise foster team warmth and collaborative energy.

Participants actively managed their emotional expressions, calibrating what they displayed to teammates in order to manage the group atmosphere while conforming to dominant norms of stoicism. One student explained, “If I have a positive emotion, I prefer to show [it] because I hope my positive emotion can affect my teammates. But if I have negative emotions... I prefer to hide them” (P21W). Another noted how visibly strained faces in the group triggered her own anxiety: “When they are really stressed, I also feel that stress” (P6W). These accounts acknowledge the contagion potential of affect and reflect a Warmth-oriented concern for team cohesion; yet the systematic suppression of anxiety simultaneously upholds MCC by relegating vulnerability to the private sphere. In protecting peers from perceived emotional “burdens,” students sacrifice opportunities to build Security and deeper relational trust—thereby narrowing the emotional bandwidth through which inclusive, collaborative learning could otherwise emerge.

Participants frequently coped with negatively valenced emotions by immersing themselves in productivity, reinforcing masculinity norms equating emotional resilience with productivity. Participant 2 explicitly used coding to distract herself emotionally:

When coding, it kind of makes me not think about the negative things because I have something else to focus on.

(P2W)

Participant 3 similarly linked managing nervousness with taking productive action:

When I felt nervous, I definitely wanted to quickly get everything going... So that's how I would describe [handling] nervousness.

(P3M)

These coping mechanisms reflect masculinity norms embedded in EE culture: emotional difficulties must be managed privately through productivity, further legitimizing masculinity ideals of self-reliance and toughness (Status), marginalizing emotional openness or collective emotional support as signs of vulnerability or weakness.

Mistakes carried a heavy emotional price, reinforcing the expectation that competent engineers should remain unflappable. One student admitted that error would leave him “quite a little bit embarrassed,” yet he would quickly “move on and talk to others to find a solution” (P24M). In sharper contrast, another participant described a cascade of self-reproach—“shame, annoyed, anger, guilt, embarrassment”—and conceded, “I don't think I would ask for help” (P23W). Both responses reveal how feelings situated in the Status dimension—guilt, shame, embarrassment—translate masculinity norms of infallibility into everyday practice. The more acute the self-consciousness, the more likely students were to retreat into solitary problem solving, sacrificing opportunities for collaborative sense-making. In this way, the emotional costs of vulnerability sustain a culture where perfectionism is prized above shared learning and mutual support.

Overall, the Show No Weakness sub-theme reflects how reproducing masculinity norms that equate vulnerability with weakness contributes to sustaining the status quo of MCC at the Swiss technical university. By suppressing emotions and presenting an unflappable front, students perpetuate a culture that values stoicism and self-reliance over openness and emotional support. This leads to the dominance of emotions such as shame and guilt, while warmth and care are undervalued. The suppression of negatively valenced emotions such as anger and anxiety prevents students

from seeking support, leading to feelings of isolation and stress. This imbalance hinders the development of supportive team relationships and negatively impacts both individual well-being and learning satisfaction. By discouraging the expression of genuine negatively valenced emotions, the competitive environment undermines collaboration and emotional connection—essential components not only for effective and satisfying learning experiences but also for potential change of the status quo.

5.1.3 | Put work first

Participants in the study often prioritized productivity and efficiency over social interactions within their team projects, embodying the “Put Work First” sub-theme. This emphasis mirrors aspects of the MCC, where overwork and suppression of personal needs are viewed as demonstrations of commitment and competence (Berdahl et al., 2018).

Participants frequently described anxiety and stress associated with maintaining institutional standards, viewing interpersonal engagement as potentially disruptive to productivity. For example, Participant 27 explained her strong preference for solitary work when asked in the context of teamwork:

Because I manage my own time, and I cannot focus a lot when I'm around many people.

(P27W)

In isolation, this quote might appear as merely a personal work preference. However, contextualizing this statement within EE's broader cultural norms highlights its deeper significance: during group collaboration, students reproduce masculinity norms emphasizing individual control, autonomy, and personal productivity as markers of professional competence. The expressed preference for working alone during teamwork thus aligns with MCC, reinforcing masculinity ideals of self-sufficiency and seriousness. This preference reflects the Status dimension, where individual work is prioritized over collective collaboration, thereby marginalizing teamwork-oriented behaviors.

Similarly, Participant 21 favored technological solutions over team-based collaboration, explicitly prioritizing productivity:

I think maybe the main reason is that compared with asking your teammates, maybe asking ChatGPT about the coding part is more efficient.

(P21W)

This perspective aligns with EE's masculine ideal of the “sole engineering genius,” characterized by independence and technological autonomy. Participant 21's behavior reinforces MCC by devaluing trust-building (Security) and relational collaboration (Warmth), instead elevating independence (Status).

The consistent prioritization of individual productivity frequently led participants to avoid interpersonal engagement, even at the cost of feeling bored or isolated. Participant 30 articulated this tension:

You finish something, then you don't want to [disturb them], because they're still working on their part. So, you don't want to disrupt them from what they're doing. So maybe you do a little bit less. So, sometimes that's why you feel bored.

(P30M)

In EE, Participant 30's reluctance to engage teammates due to productivity pressures illustrates suppression of relational needs typical of MCC, where emotions associated with Security and Warmth are sacrificed to maintain Status. His boredom thus signals a deeper emotional dissonance—he suppresses relational needs to maintain alignment with masculinity norms of self-control and efficiency, legitimizing unequal gender relations in which emotional openness is marginalized.

Participant 2 similarly refrained from interacting based on visual cues indicating her teammates' intense concentration:

I can tell whether they are focusing... If their smile disappears, I think they enter a focus state... So, yeah, I will not interrupt them at this point.

(P2W)

Contextualizing this within EE, the absence of emotional engagement (not interrupting others) signals adherence to MCC, marginalizing emotional expressions related to Security (vulnerability) or Warmth (social engagement), perpetuating unequal gender relations by sustaining masculinity expectations for productivity over relationships.

Despite these negative consequences, students derived emotional rewards, such as pride and satisfaction, from meeting high productivity standards. Participant 7 reflected on this dynamic:

When you see the fruits of your labor, it's an exceptional feeling of satisfaction, and it drives you to repeat the cycle... even if to achieve it you have to go through phases of frustration and stress, but in the end, it's worth it.

(P7M)

Within the competitive environment of EE, personal success, particularly under conditions of stress or hardship, aligns strongly with masculinity ideals such as resilience, strength, and endurance. Participant 7's comment underscores how positively valenced emotional rewards (satisfaction, pride) reinforce students' commitment to masculinity practices, despite experiencing affective dissonance, thus maintaining the MCC.

Overall, the "Put Work First" sub-theme reflects masculinity practices defined by prioritizing personal achievement and productivity, rooted deeply in the MCC prevalent in EE. Participants reproduced these practices through social-emotional behaviors that emphasize the Status dimension—displaying emotional restraint, self-reliance, and independence—even as this behavior undermined their experience of Security and Warmth. By explicitly connecting these practices to masculinity norms embedded in engineering's cultural context, our data illustrate how these hegemonic masculinities shape students' emotional experiences, satisfaction, and interpersonal dynamics within team projects.

5.2 | Counterhegemonic practices

Contrasting with the previous theme, the theme Counterhegemonic Practices captures participants' efforts to disrupt the reproduction of masculinity norms by questioning established hierarchical structures and promoting collaboration and emotional support. Importantly, both hegemonic and counterhegemonic practices persisted throughout the project, with the same individuals often exhibiting both types of practices at different times, suggesting that hegemonic and counterhegemonic practices exist on a spectrum within individuals rather than as binary opposites—a complexity we further discuss in the Discussion section.

5.2.1 | Questioning the status quo

The Questioning the Status Quo sub-theme highlights participants' reflective efforts—primarily occurring during interviews, where they had dedicated space and time to articulate and evaluate their emotional experiences—to challenge the prevailing masculinity norms of competition, emotional suppression, and hierarchical dynamics within their teams. By naming and expressing emotions evoked by problematic practices in the interviews, participants made visible and disrupted the unequal gender relations typically legitimized by MCC.

For instance, Participant 26 openly expressed frustration about being disregarded by teammates, explicitly challenging the hierarchical dynamics that privilege dominant voices:

Because last year I did a project with five people, which was actually pretty much that situation during the whole thing. So, it just wasn't as good as I hoped it would be. I know we could have done better if they just listened to me a little more.

(P26W)

By voicing her frustration (Status dimension), Participant 26 made visible how masculinity norms systematically marginalized her contributions. Her emotional openness signaled resistance to the MCC norm of silencing less dominant team members, thus contesting gendered power relations by advocating for equal participation.

Similarly, Participant 22 questioned the emphasis on individualism and the lack of inclusive communication typical of MCC:

Everyone was talking but not listening to each other, so it was like everyone wanted to go in a separate way... I didn't understand what we were going towards... It feels like they know but they don't tell you, and actually, they don't even know because they don't talk.

(P22M)

His explicit identification of fragmented communication directly challenges MCC norms that valorize individualistic competition over collaborative clarity. Through frustration and confusion, he rendered visible the harmful effects of masculinity competition on team cohesion and emotional trust, encouraging reflection on collaborative alternatives.

Several students explicitly questioned the idea rooted in MCC that professionalism requires emotional distance. Looking back on her project, Participant 27 lamented, "It's such a shame that we didn't have that group atmosphere... we didn't have that thing that makes everyone talk" (P27W). Participant 16 echoed the sentiment: "Maybe more social interactions... the social part is the one missing" (P16W). By foregrounding what they called the "missing" Warmth of informal conversation and shared rapport, both students exposed the relational deficits that arise when teams focus solely on technical output. Their critiques underscore that learning suffers when opportunities for connection and mutual support are sidelined in favor of detached, performance-oriented masculinities.

Participants openly challenged practices of individualism that undermined collaborative responsibility. Participant 26 explicitly confronted teammates who prioritized personal interests over team goals, particularly describing a situation during the final project preparation week, when the team was expected to be collaboratively focused on coding tasks and integrating results. Instead of participating in this crucial joint effort, one teammate diverted their attention to booking personal travels:

Why are you doing this? We're supposed to work and do it all together. Why are you... booking flights for something else...

(P26W)

Expressing anger and frustration specifically about unequal contributions during this critical collaborative period highlighted the problematic nature of MCC's prioritization of individual pursuits over shared goals. Her resistance articulated relational accountability, critiquing gendered practices where individualism directly disrupted collective cohesion, trust, and mutual support in the team.

Humor and shared enjoyment surfaced as deliberate counterhegemonic practices for cultivating team cohesion. Participant 4 explained that sprinkling jokes into meetings "gives good energy to the group" (P4M). Similarly, Participant 7 recalled project sessions that "might have been fun," noting that 6 weeks of collaboration created "an affinity with certain members... we had a laugh" (P7M). By actively inviting laughter and rapport, these students pushed back against the MCC assumption that engineering work must remain emotionally restrained. Their experiences show how Warmth-oriented practices can generate positive affect, reinforce interpersonal bonds, and broaden the emotional space in which collaborative learning unfolds.

Feelings of boredom arising from emotional detachment prompted participants to question MCC's emphasis on solitary productivity. Participant 30 advocated for more engagement:

It's maybe due to the lack of interaction. I felt that when we were interacting a lot, I was feeling excited... you feel better usually.

(P30M)

Participant 20 expressed similar sentiments regarding lack of connection within the team:

I'd say kind of bored. It's just because we weren't interacting that much... we didn't talk that much because we didn't have a lot of time... So, I'd say that just made me feel bored.

(P20M)

Their explicit emotional critique of solitary work practices highlights MCC's neglect of relational engagement, challenging masculinity norms by promoting communication and mutual support.

Participants actively advocated for inclusive dialogue and patience, explicitly resisting MCC norms of immediate competence and intolerance for mistakes. Participant 15 emphasized supportive communication:

You cannot expect someone to be like this [not making mistakes]. You have to give them time and re-explain.

(P15M)

His statement challenged EE norms that discourage showing vulnerability or uncertainty, instead advocating for patience and collaborative support, thereby making visible the negative impact of these masculinity norms on learning and collaboration.

Overall, participants' efforts to question and challenge the masculinity status quo through emotional openness (frustration, anger, empathy, humor, hope) illustrate powerful counterhegemonic practices. By naming problematic behaviors and unequal gender relations, they began the necessary work of making these inequalities visible—an essential precursor to dismantling them. Nevertheless, the persistent dominance of MCC's norms and cultural values makes sustained systemic change challenging, often resulting in feelings of discouragement and impacting students' satisfaction with their learning experiences. Despite this, the emotional and social critiques participants articulated lay crucial groundwork for fostering more inclusive and supportive learning environments.

5.2.2 | Collaboration over competition

The Collaboration Over Competition sub-theme highlights how participants prioritized teamwork and mutual support within their project teams, challenging competitive norms and prioritization of work over relationships. By embracing cooperation and collective success over individual achievement, participants engaged in counterhegemonic practices that fostered inclusive environments and undermined the dominance of the MCC.

Participants consistently articulated the positive impact of collaboration on team productivity and individual learning experiences. Participant 34 highlighted transparency and mutual support:

When working in a team, you need good cooperation... we communicated very transparently... that gave us more productivity and simply more efficiency.

(P34M)

Explicitly advocating transparent communication signals resistance to MCC's emotional suppression and competitive individualism. This practice promotes Security and Warmth dimensions, explicitly challenging MCC's emphasis on status-based competition and solitary productivity.

Participant 30 similarly expressed satisfaction in collaborative idea-sharing:

When we interact to give more ideas and we learn a bit more about what everyone is doing, so it affected positively when I interacted with others.

(P30M)

The joy and satisfaction linked to collaborative learning explicitly counter MCC that value individual productivity over relational connection. By valuing interactions and sharing knowledge, Participant 30 fosters emotionally rewarding practices that challenge masculinity norms emphasizing independence and solitary productivity, thereby promoting belonging within the team.

Several students openly valued one another's expertise, challenging the MCC ideal of self-reliance. Participant 11 described how a teammate “was good at the programming language and helped me with it... my teammate helped me understand” (P11M), expressing gratitude rather than competitive defensiveness. Participant 1 echoed this stance, noting that “teammates can point out which is more important, which we should focus on... this is a very important point” (P1M). By acknowledging personal limits and welcoming guidance, both students reframed vulnerability as a

collective asset, shifting team culture from solitary performance toward mutual learning and Security and Warmth-oriented engagement.

Participants expressed positive emotional surprise at the depth of their team connections, challenging MCC's norm of emotional restraint. Participant 28 articulated this emotional shift:

[I was pleasantly surprised] Because I didn't expect to be able to like them, to bond with them, create a friendly environment.

(P28W)

Her surprise and joy explicitly reveal the emotional and relational deficits embedded within MCC, making visible marginalization of openness and vulnerability. Participant 28's emotional recognition signals deliberate resistance to MCC by embracing the Warmth dimension—valuing connection and relational bonds over emotional detachment.

Participant 15 similarly experienced relief and emotional growth explicitly through collaboration:

And relief, yeah, definitely made me feel better and more relaxed, a better person, I would say.

(P15M)

The explicit articulation of relief and personal development through collaboration communicates resistance to MCC's individualism and emotional suppression. Such emotional expressions function as counterhegemonic signals, highlighting how relational practices emotionally enhance team learning experiences.

Participants further promoted emotional openness by normalizing mistakes, challenging MCC's perfectionism. Participant 23 acknowledged the acceptability of mistakes:

I wouldn't have really minded. I mean, it's okay. We all make mistakes.

(P23W)

This acceptance of mistakes (Security) directly contests MCC's marginalization of vulnerability or imperfection as threats to status. Participant 23's emotional openness fosters an inclusive environment by dismantling emotional hierarchies based on perfectionism.

A transparent division of work emerged as another counterhegemonic practice for fostering collaboration over competition. Reflecting on a key turning point in her project, Participant 14 noted, "Since the base was settled, now tasks were more specific... We split the task, and yeah, we all did something." (P14W). By transparently distributing responsibilities rather than allowing a few individuals to monopolize the most prestigious tasks, the team built mutual respect and trust. This practice challenged the Status-oriented logic of MCC and fostered a more egalitarian dynamic that valued each member's contribution and strengthened the group's sense of cohesion.

Participants advocated inclusive leadership practices to engage quieter or less visible team members, directly countering MCC norms of authoritative control. Participant 26 sought to engage less vocal teammates:

I always try to talk to the ones who don't talk too much... I try to do it. But sometimes... they don't try to continue. So I'm not going to force anything.

(P26W)

Engaging quieter teammates signals resistance to MCC's expectations that privilege assertive, dominant voices. Participant 26's approach fosters emotional Security (trust, support) and Warmth (compassion, care).

Overall, by embracing collaboration over competition, participants disrupted the dominance of assertion and power typically aimed at constructing hegemonic masculinities. This approach enhanced team cohesion and satisfaction with learning experiences, reduced stress, and led to positively valenced emotions such as satisfaction, admiration, and joy in learning experiences. Participants' actions demonstrate the benefits of integrating the Security and Warmth dimensions of social emotions into team dynamics, challenging masculinity norms and fostering a more inclusive environment and better learning experiences.

5.2.3 | Emotional support

The Emotional Support sub-theme illustrates how participants embraced empathy, open emotional expression, and mutual care within their team projects. This approach challenges the MCC “Show No Weakness” norm that demands the suppression of vulnerability (Berdahl et al., 2018). By prioritizing emotional awareness and support, participants engaged in counterhegemonic practices that fostered inclusive and cohesive team dynamics and ultimately contributed to greater satisfaction with learning experiences.

Participants emphasized attentiveness to teammates’ emotional states, prioritizing empathy, compassion, and care—key features of the Security and Warmth dimensions. Participant 3 demonstrated empathy by expressing concern for a teammate’s well-being:

I saw him sometimes... a thinking emotion, maybe when you’re trying to figure something out. It definitely triggered my interest in understanding if everything is okay with him, where he is at on his task.

(P3M)

By recognizing and responding empathetically to a teammate’s emotional cues, Participant 3 challenged MCC’s emotional detachment. His empathy communicates resistance by valuing relational care over individualism, making visible and contesting unequal gender relations embedded in emotional suppression norms.

Participant 24 highlighted how attentiveness to teammates’ emotions influenced his behavior:

I do change my action toward somebody based on what they are feeling now...

(P24M)

This emotional responsiveness promotes relational care and trust, contesting MCC’s expectation that professionalism in EE requires emotional indifference. Participant 24’s deliberate practice of emotional adaptability counters norms that marginalize emotional vulnerability, legitimizing emotionally responsive behaviors within the team projects.

Participants advocated for openly communicating negatively valenced emotions rather than suppressing them, challenging MCC’s emotional restraint. Participant 11 described the value of emotional openness:

I think you should express your [negative] feelings; you should not hide them... you need to confront it so that you can get over it.

(P11M)

His explicit encouragement of emotional expression resists MCC’s equating vulnerability with weakness, promoting trust and collaboration. By embracing emotional openness, Participant 11 contests masculinity norms, visibly disrupting unequal gender relations.

Female participants articulated emotional openness as an effective way to build deeper connections, resisting masculinity norms that discourage emotional vulnerability. Participant 2 described emotional expression as integral to forming authentic connections:

If I’m working with my friends... I prefer to speak out my negative emotions directly... I will feel better if they have the same feeling with me... it’s like some kind of connection.

(P2W)

Participant 2’s preference for emotional sharing explicitly challenges MCC’s marginalization of vulnerability, especially for women who may face greater scrutiny for emotional openness. Her emotional practice highlights and resists gender norms, making visible inequalities tied to gender expectations of emotional restraint, thus fostering egalitarian emotional relations.

However, some participants also acknowledged complexities around emotional openness, particularly in international or unfamiliar team contexts. Participant 10 described her hesitance in openly sharing emotions in such environments:

I don't want them [team members] to know me too much... I just want to express that feeling to the people that I trust.

(P10W)

Participant 10's emotional hesitation explicitly makes visible the internal conflict engendered by MCC norms—navigating between the desire for authentic connection (Security) and masculinity expectations for emotional restraint in EE (Status). By articulating this tension, she reveals the emotional cost of MCC's emotional expectations, thus contributing to the visibility and critique of unequal gender relations.

Overall, by focusing on emotional support, participants prioritized team well-being over rigid masculinity norms. This practice aligns with counterhegemonic practices, promoting empathy, open communication, and mutual support (Messerschmidt, 2018). It shifts emphasis from the Status dimension to the Security and Warmth dimensions, fostering trust, compassion, and cohesion. This shift not only improved learning experiences but also contributed to dismantling the status quo of MCC. Embracing vulnerability allowed participants to address issues more effectively and build deeper connections, enhancing both individual well-being and collaborative learning. By challenging the expectation of “Show No Weakness,” participants promoted and experienced a more inclusive and collaborative team culture, demonstrating how counterhegemonic practices can lead to healthier and more effective team environments.

6 | DISCUSSION

This study explored how computer science students' social emotions and the (re)construction of masculinities influence their satisfaction with learning during team projects. Our findings demonstrate how social emotions are expressed—and which emotions are deemed acceptable—become a vehicle through which gendered power relations are played out in everyday interactions, thereby significantly impacting students' learning satisfaction.

Students experienced a spectrum of social emotions during their team projects, including both negatively valenced (e.g., anger, frustration, shame, guilt, anxiety) and positively valenced (e.g., admiration, joy, and satisfaction). In line with Tormey's (2021) three-dimensional model (Status, Security, Warmth) and the Emotions as Social Information theory (van Kleef & Côté, 2022), these emotions operated as social signals, allowing us to interpret the social meaning of interactions without direct inquiry. For example, emotions such as anger and pride were frequently mobilized by participants to assert dominance or defend individual competence, thus enacting hegemonic masculinities through the prioritization of Status. Conversely, expressions of empathy, sadness, and relief signaled recognition of relational needs, challenging the masculinity norms of emotional stoicism and work over relations, thereby representing counterhegemonic practices and endorsing Security and Warmth dimensions.

Hegemonic masculinities were prominent in the Swiss technical university setting, with students often reproducing norms of competitiveness, emotional suppression, and individualism prevalent in EE via emotional expressions aligned with the Status dimension (Garr-Schultz et al., 2023; Lo Andersson & Landström, 2023; Secules, 2019). Suppressing emotions such as frustration and shame aligned with the MCC's “Show No Weakness” norm, discouraging vulnerability (Berdahl et al., 2018). This reinforces the “rational engineer” archetype and prioritizes Status over Security and Warmth in social emotions (Lo Andersson & Landström, 2023; Tormey, 2021).

Conversely, counterhegemonic practices emerged distinctly when participants openly expressed emotions conducive to collaboration, connection, and mutual care, such as empathy, relief, and even frustration regarding exclusion. These emotions, contextually arising within team projects, challenged hegemonic masculinities by rendering unequal gender relations visible, advocating for more inclusive interactions. Expressions of sadness or frustration related to alienation directly opposed MCC norms, while satisfaction or joy derived from collaborative achievements provided evidence of how emotional openness and mutual support can foster inclusive team dynamics.

Enforcing the expression of “right” emotions per MCC not only sustains an exclusionary masculinity culture but negatively affects all students, regardless of gender, by diverting attention from systemic team issues to individual emotional management (Benschop & Lewis, 2024). Suppressing emotions perpetuates a culture valuing stoicism, marginalizing those who do not conform, as participants feared being seen as weak or unprofessional if they expressed negatively valenced emotions, thereby reinforcing the heteronormative gender system in EE (Cech & Waidzun, 2011). The valorization of positivity compels individuals to produce “economically valuable” emotions while suppressing “bad feelings” (i.e., engage in a byproductive labor; see Whitney, 2018), aligning with postfeminist

and neoliberal ideologies that individualize structural inequalities by framing them as personal psychological barriers to be overcome (Benschop & Lewis, 2024).

The interplay between social emotions and masculinities clearly affected students' learning satisfaction. Participants embodying hegemonic masculinities by suppressing emotions reported reduced satisfaction, heightened stress, and impaired team cohesion, experiencing frustration, isolation, and affective dissonance. Rodríguez-Simmonds et al. (2023) observed a similar dynamic in an all-men capstone team, where a shared masculine identity emphasizing technical competence and individual productivity discouraged relational engagement, leading to uneven inclusion, diminished feelings of belonging, and differential learning experiences among team members. Conversely, those who enacted counterhegemonic practices—openly sharing emotions, providing emotional support, and emphasizing collaboration—often reported greater satisfaction with learning and stronger interpersonal relationships in our research, disrupting the dominance of the Status and promoting the Security and Warmth dimensions.

An important finding is the temporal consistency of both hegemonic and counterhegemonic practices throughout the projects. Interviews conducted at different project stages showed that these dynamics persisted over time, with the same individuals often exhibiting both hegemonic and counterhegemonic practices. This indicates that masculinities are not binary but exist along a spectrum within individuals, regardless of their self-identified gender, thereby complicating systemic change because students may revert to hegemonic practices even after attempting to adopt counterhegemonic ones. Effective disruption of the status quo requires sustained interventions addressing this fluidity.

Consistently across both interview phases, codes related to hegemonic masculinities were twice as prevalent as those related to counterhegemonic practices. The prevalence of hegemonic masculinities is unsurprising given that University 1 consistently is often seen as an elite technical university not only in Europe but globally. Such a portrayal may attract and select students who have been exhibiting hegemonic masculinities even before enrolling there. For these students, holding a hegemonic position can offer significant advantages, such as gaining access to resources, recognition, and opportunities that reinforce their status within the academic environment.

6.1 | Future research

Future research should address the untapped potential of social emotions in driving systemic change within EE. Creating a space for expressions of negatively valenced emotions in team projects is not only socially advantageous (see Kavanagh et al., 2024) but also can challenge and transform the entrenched harmful masculinity culture, which would be beneficial for all genders (for a similar argument, see Riley, 2013). For instance, by exploring how students express “bad feelings,” researchers can identify opportunities for students to externalize their experiences, recognize shared challenges, and mobilize collective efforts to address systemic issues such as exclusion, harassment, or discrimination (see Bleijenbergh, 2024; Hemmings, 2012). Some participants reported that expressing negatively valenced emotions is a healthy coping mechanism, supporting the idea that sharing emotions can prevent individual burdens and catalyze collective efforts (see Benschop & Lewis, 2024). Furthermore, future studies could extend current research by examining whether—and how—the emotional and masculinity practices identified here persist or transform in professional engineering workplaces, where inter-team and inter-firm competition is often more pronounced.

Building on growing literature on how norm violators gain influence (van Kleef, 2023), future research might investigate whether deliberately deviating from masculinity norms in EE can function as a strategic lever for altering power dynamics. Specifically, studies could assess whether counterhegemonic practices lead to increased social capital, peer recognition, and leadership opportunities. This direction has the potential to bridge research on norm violations and social influence with our findings on how social emotions underpin and contest the construction of masculinities in EE, thereby providing insights into the pathways through which counterhegemonic practices can transform team dynamics and challenge entrenched gender hierarchies.

6.2 | Practical implications

Hegemonic masculinities harm team dynamics by promoting competitive individualism and emotional restraint. In contrast, counterhegemonic practices that encourage collaboration, emotional expression, and mutual support improve team cohesion and learning experiences. To enhance learning and mitigate the negative effects of masculinities, educators and institutions should implement interventions that help individuals overcome obstacles, provide social support,

offer incentives, and highlight inclusive social norms—which were found to be effective at changing behavior (Albarracín et al., 2024). The suggested recommendations below flow directly from the three sub-themes presented in Section 5: guidance on incentives targets students' accounts of competitive individualism; calls for structured reflection address their experiences of emotional suppression; and suggestions for teacher-led modeling build on the counterhegemonic moments participants themselves enacted.

A distinctive implication of this study is that providing a reflective space—often missing in EE—allowed participants to name and critically reflect upon their social and emotional experiences, thereby revealing how hegemonic masculinities manifest in everyday interactions. By naming emotions, students reflected upon power dynamics embedded in the MCC, thinking about how emotional suppression and the emphasis on individual achievement affect their learning experiences. In this way, the interview process functioned as both an analytical and a transformative tool, sharpening awareness of socio-emotional norms and providing participants with space to critique them. We recommend that practitioners develop similar reflective opportunities within educational settings to foster inclusive practices.

Recognizing that team projects serve as microcosms for broader social realities in EE, our findings suggest that making masculinities visible through explicit emotional reflection can pave the way for effective interventions. Accordingly, Table A1 in Appendix A outlines potential strategies, inspired by the 3 T PLAY approach (Isaac & de Lima, 2024), to reduce the impact of hegemonic masculinities and foster counterhegemonic practices, enhancing learning experiences in team projects. This approach integrates key aspects of transversal skill development—knowing, experiencing, and learning from experiencing. Moreover, teaching assistants (TAs) play a crucial role due to their intermediary position between faculty and students. TAs can thus model inclusive behaviors, facilitate discussions on team dynamics, support transversal skills development, and act as intermediaries to challenge masculinity norms. By engaging with the 3 T PLAY framework, TAs can help create environments that challenge hegemonic masculinities and support improved learning experiences.

6.3 | Limitations

While providing novel insights, this research has limitations. First, although the authors' disciplinary diversity enriched perspectives, having different authors conduct interviews and perform analyses may have influenced the findings. This separation could have introduced variations in understanding participants' responses and their experiences, potentially affecting analysis consistency. To reduce this risk, a shared interview schedule was used, but we acknowledge that the person of the researcher is part of the data collection and thus this may have impacted some interviews.

Second, gender norms are deeply influenced by social location, cultural context, time, and age (Messerschmidt, 2018; Wong & Wang, 2022). Therefore, hegemonic masculinities and counterhegemonic practices may vary in different contexts. Our goal was not to generalize empirically but to provide a framework for others to apply in their contexts, supported by contextual information about our universities.

Third, the lack of diversity concerning gender identity and other intersecting social identities should be noted. In University 1, about 3% of students identify with a gender other than the binary categories of women and men. Unfortunately, none volunteered to participate in our study, leaving transgender, non-binary, and gender-nonconforming experiences underexplored. This omission limits our findings' comprehensiveness, overlooking unique challenges faced by individuals outside the gender binary. Lastly, participants were not asked about other identity aspects such as ethnicity, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, or disability. While some intersectional aspects (e.g., language and gender) emerged, our study could not fully capture the diverse experiences of all students within engineering team projects.

7 | CONCLUSION

Our study explored the presence of social emotions in engineering student project teams and how they influence satisfaction with learning experiences through their interplay with masculinities. Applying a three-dimensional model of social emotions, we analyzed how discrete emotions positioned individuals within their teams in terms of Status (dominance), Security (psychological safety), and Warmth (belonging). This analytical lens allowed us to interpret emotions such as anger, shame, boredom, guilt, disappointment, pride, frustration, sadness, compassion, hope, awe, and gratitude, revealing how these emotions enacted either hegemonic or counterhegemonic practices. Through inductive coding, MCC emerged as a powerful explanatory framework highlighting competitive individualism, prioritization of

work over personal and social well-being, and valorization of endurance and strength. Notably, both hegemonic and counterhegemonic practices were observed across genders and within the same individuals, underscoring tensions rooted in broader cultural dynamics rather than gender-based differences. These dynamics persisted consistently throughout team projects, indicating they were not confined to specific teamwork stages. Students enacting hegemonic masculinities typically suppressed negatively valenced emotions, which resulted in decreased satisfaction, increased stress, feelings of alienation, and hindered team cohesion and learning. In contrast, counterhegemonic practices—characterized by emotional openness, mutual support, and collaboration—fostered positively valenced emotions, enhanced team cohesion and productivity, and promoted shared learning and mutual respect.

Cumulatively, linking appraisal-based emotion approaches with masculinities-as-practice moves EE research beyond static gender comparisons toward a dynamic account of how status, security, and warmth are negotiated through everyday feelings. Practically, our findings point to three levers for change: (i) recalibrating incentives to account for team success more than individual rankings, (ii) embedding guided emotional reflection in project cycles, and (iii) engaging educators and teaching assistants in modeling caring, collaborative norms. Creating spaces for these counterhegemonic practices is essential for improving engineering students' learning experiences.

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ORCID

Vladislav Krivoshekov <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1213-0884>

Nihat Kotluk <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4314-9492>

Yoann Favre <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4378-5480>

Marina Fiori <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2004-7458>

Egon Werlen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5550-7552>

Roland Tormey <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2502-9451>

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Vladislav Krivoshchekov is a social scientist at the Teaching Support Centre at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland.

Nihat Kotluk is a learning scientist and pedagogical advisor at the Teaching Support Centre at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland.

Yoann Favre is a PhD student at the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training, Renens, Switzerland.

Marina Fiori is a professor and head of the research field “Learning Processes and Support” at the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training, Renens, Switzerland.

Egon Werlen is a professor and head of the research field “Emotions, Reading and Learning” at the Swiss Distance University of Applied Sciences, Brig, Switzerland.

Roland Tormey is a senior scientist and head of service at the Teaching Support Centre at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland.

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APPENDIX A: Interview Protocol

The questions were prepared based on the multi-component model of emotions (Scherer, 2005).

Interview 1 Protocol

Overarching question: How do emotional experiences during group work influence student' learning, performance, and team dynamics in computer science education?

Section 1: Introduction: [4–5 min]

Greet participant, introduce the study and interviewer.

Explain purpose: understand emotional experiences in team settings.

Explain that this is the first of two interviews, focusing on background and emotional experiences in group settings.

Emphasize confidentiality, data anonymization, and ethical handling.

Request consent for recording.

Duration: 50–60 min.

Section 2: Warm-up Questions [5–7 min]

Background of the participant

1. To start, could you briefly introduce yourself and share some background details to better understand your viewpoints and experiences?
2. Do you prefer to study/work, alone or in a group? Why?
3. Do you have any prior experience working or studying in team settings, group discussions, or team projects?

Section 3: Core Questions [35–40 min]: Emotional Experiences in Group Work

[Stimulus for Cognitive Appraisal]

The main question 1: Since the beginning of the semester, I would like to know how you felt during the group activities. Can you tell me about a moment or a specific situation when you felt some emotions? [For example, during these group activities, were there moments or situations when you felt bored, angry, enjoyed, happy, got frustrated, felt sad, experienced disappointment, felt guilty, felt insecure, found it insincere, embarrassed, or proud?]

[Subjective Experience (Emotional Experience/Affective State/Subjective Feeling)]

The main question 2: Can you share with me what you were feeling during that specific moment? I mean what emotions did you start to experience? [if needed, show the wheel of emotions (Scherer, 2005)].

[Verbalization of Emotional Experiences]

The main question 3: How would you explain/describe the emotions you felt in that moment? What words would you prefer to describe your feelings at that time? [if needed, ask which emoji you would prefer to use to describe that emotion?]

[Internal Bodily Changes (Physiological Reactions)]

The main question 4: What kind of physiological reactions did you experience in your body when you felt those emotions at that moment? (such as changes in heart rate, palms sweating, or rapid breathing?)

[Cognitive Appraisal (Assessment of Personal Meaning)]

The main question 5: Why did you feel that way in those moments or situations? Or why were the reasons or triggers important to you?

[Facial Expressions and Non-Verbal Communication]

The main question 6: What changes did you notice in your groupmates' facial expressions or postures at that moment? (Alternatively, were there any non-verbal cues or facial expressions you observed in your group members during that moment?)

[Thought–Action Tendencies (Motivates to Think and Act)]

The main question 7: What did you do or want to do during that moment or situation? (Alternatively; when you were feeling those emotions, did you want to do something or act in a certain way?)

[Response to Emotion (Coping and Reacting to Emotion)]

The main question 8: How did you manage or react to your emotions during that moment? Were there any specific strategies or actions you took to handle/cope with the situation?

[The effects of social emotions experienced: How emotions affected their learning, team dynamics and outcomes]

The main question 9: How did those emotions enhance or hinder your performance? (How did those emotions affect your ability to contribute to the discussion and your overall learning experience during the team/group project/discussion? Did those moments of feeling make it easier or harder for you to join in and learn during the team project or group discussion?)

Closing: [2–3 min]

Ask if the participant has any questions or comments. Thank them for their participation and restate the importance of their contribution. Remind them of confidentiality and follow-up possibilities.

Interview 2 Protocol

Overarching Question: How do students perceive and respond to emotional and social dynamics during team projects, and how do these experiences affect their collaboration and outcomes?

Section 1: Introduction: [4–5 min]

Greeting the participants and thanking them for returning for the second interview.

Explain the session will last 50–60 min and will be recorded with their consent.

Ensure them of confidentiality and ethical handling of data.

Section 2: Warm-up Questions [5–7 min]

As a team, you completed the project on time, and you presented your language learning app in the final week.

1. Are you satisfied with your team's final product? (Why?)
2. Would you prefer to work in the same team (with the same members) on future projects? (Why?)
3. Are you satisfied with your team members' interactions during the process? I mean, have you had enough interactions with the team members? [if needed, ask *if you rate the level of interactions in your team from 1 (almost no interaction) to 5 (highly interactive), at what level would you rate it?*]

Section 3: Core Questions [35–40 min]

3. A. General overview of the team

Considering the interactions with and among your team members throughout the team sessions, from the first to the last one:

1. Were there any moments that you felt excluded? (when, where, why, how)
2. Do you think some team members felt excluded during the project?
3. Do you think there was competition in your team?
4. Do you think there was someone who tried to get leadership?
5. Do you feel that you or others could make some mistakes related to the project without concern? [What did you feel when you made a mistake during the project?] What did you feel when someone made a mistake during the project?

3. B. Team's emotional atmosphere

Considering the general emotional atmosphere of the team for the whole process:

1. What emotions would you like to choose to describe the overall emotional atmosphere of your team meetings? [*What emotions would I see on the roof of your team if I had glasses to see the emotions?*]
2. What are the two emotions that would define perfectly your team's atmosphere? [*I will share an emotional wheel with you. Could you please select at least two emotions from the wheel and then rate the intensity of the emotions from 1 (not at all) to 5 (the highest level)?*]

And, what about your emotions:

1. What are the two emotions that would ideally define your emotional experiences during the teamwork?

3.C. Personal Emotional Experiences

Now, I want you to think about the team meetings from the first one to the last one. Please focus on remembering the interactions with and among your team members.

[Stimulus for Cognitive Appraisal]

1. Could you please focus on specific moments/situations in which you started to feel emotions in respect to team members (s)? Not only because of your team members' behavior, act, or attitude toward you but also toward other team members.
2. What happened at that moment? What did he/she/they do to activate your emotions?

[Subjective Experience (Emotional Experience/Affective State/Subjective Feeling)]

1. As you assessed the situation/moment, what emotions did you start to experience? [Can you share with me what you were feeling emotionally during that moment? How did you feel? *(If needed you can use this wheel of emotions)*]
2. Could you please rate the intensity of the emotions [from 1 (not at all) to 5 (the highest level)?] that you experienced at that moment?

[Internal Bodily Changes (Physiological Reactions)]

1. Where exactly in your body did you feel those emotions?
2. What kind of physiological reactions did you experience in your body when you felt those emotions at that moment? Did you notice any specific physiological reactions during that moment, such as changes in heart rate, sweating palms, or rapid breathing?

[Cognitive Appraisal (Assessment of Personal Meaning)]

1. Why did their behavior, act, or attitude affect you in that way? [*What did you think at that moment? Why was that behavior important to you? What was the main trigger? What was the main reason?*]

[Facial Expressions and Non-Verbal Communication]

1. What changes did you notice in your groupmates' facial expressions (such as angry or smiling faces) or postures at that moment?
 - a. At that moment did you display your emotions on your face or with your non-verbal cues such as posture?
 - b. In general, do you display your emotions on your face, or do you hide them? Why?
 - c. Do you think your facial expression affected your teammates' interaction?
 - d. Could they understand your emotions from your face?
2. Were there any moments when your teammate' facial expressions or non-verbal communication cues affected your performance or interactions while working on the project in the team with them?

[Thought–Action Tendencies (Motivates to Think and Act)]

1. What did you do during that moment or situation? And, indeed, what did you want to do?

[Response to Emotion (Coping and Reacting to Emotion)]

1. How did you manage or react to your emotions during that moment? Were there any specific strategies or actions you took to handle/cope with the situation?

[The effects of social emotions experienced: How emotions affected their learning, team dynamics, and outcomes]

1. How did those emotions enhance or hinder your performance, learning, and interactions with others?
 - a. Performance in the team in terms of product contributions
 - b. Learning in terms of content knowledge
 - c. Interactions with others.

Closing: [2–3 min]

Ask for final reflections: most positive/negative experience, sense of team, what is missing. Thank them for their valuable input and confirm if follow-up is possible. Mention any incentives and close the session.

TABLE A1 Strategies to address masculinities in engineering education inspired by the 3 T PLAY framework.

Aspect	Recommendation	Link to masculinities and emotions in engineering education	Implementation strategies	Role of teaching assistants	Expected outcomes
1. Incorporate the Knowing Aspect	Educate engineering students about team dynamics, emotions, and the impact of masculinities on collaboration within engineering projects.	By teaching concepts related to masculinities and the role of emotions in engineering team interactions, students become aware of how rigid masculinity norms influence behavior and team dynamics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate modules on emotions: Include lectures or workshops on emotional awareness and regulation in engineering curricula. - Discuss masculinity norms: Facilitate discussions examining rigid masculinity norms in engineering culture. - Provide engineering-specific frameworks: Introduce models like agile methodologies and interdisciplinary teamwork strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assist in creating and delivering content: TAs can help present and/or create materials on team dynamics, emotions, and masculinities. - Share personal experiences: TAs can share observations of masculinities and emotions in engineering. - Encourage critical thinking: TAs can prompt students to reflect on how rigid masculinity norms affect behavior. 	- Students understand how actions and emotional expressions affect team dynamics and project outcomes. Awareness empowers students to choose inclusive behaviors that enhance collaboration and innovation in engineering.
2. Emphasize the Experiencing Aspect	Design low-risk, experiential learning activities that promote collaboration, emotional expression, and inclusive practices within engineering contexts.	Engaging in activities that require teamwork and open communication allows students to practice counterhegemonic behaviors, challenging rigid masculinity norms in engineering.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use tangible engineering projects: Employ hands-on team activities focusing on process over product. - Set open-ended challenges: Design problems requiring collective problem-solving without predetermined outcomes (e.g., sustainable energy solutions). - Facilitate role-playing exercises: Encourage role-play in scenarios that require expressing vulnerability or providing emotional support in engineering contexts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate activities: TAs can lead experiential learning activities, ensuring inclusive participation. - Guide role-playing exercises: TAs can support students during role-play and debrief effectively. - Provide a safe space: TAs can create an environment where students feel comfortable practicing new behaviors. 	- Students experience positive effects of collaboration and emotional openness in projects. Activities help reduce influence of masculinities by normalizing inclusive behaviors and emotional expression in engineering contexts.

TABLE A1 (Continued)

Aspect	Recommendation	Link to masculinities and emotions in engineering education	Implementation strategies	Role of teaching assistants	Expected outcomes
3. Implement Learning from Experience	Incorporate structured reflection sessions to help engineering students internalize their experiences and apply lessons to future engineering projects.	Reflective practices enable students to examine how masculinities and emotional dynamics affect their interactions and learning experiences in engineering.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate guided reflection: Lead debriefing sessions post-activities to discuss successes, challenges, and emotional roles in engineering processes. - Promote metacognitive skills: Encourage thinking about thinking and behaviors within engineering tasks. - Assign reflective journals: Have students record experiences, emotions, and insights regarding team interactions and project development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lead reflection sessions: TAs can conduct debriefings to help students connect experiences to learning objectives. - Encourage metacognition: TAs can prompt students to consider their behaviors and attitudes - Offer individualized feedback: TAs can provide personalized insights on teamwork and emotional intelligence skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students gain deeper understanding of the interplay between masculinities, emotions, and teamwork. - Reflection aids in transferring skills to new contexts, reinforcing counterhegemonic practices in future engineering projects.
4. Foster a Supportive Learning Environment	Create an engineering classroom culture that values inclusivity, emotional safety, and mutual respect.	A supportive environment reduces pressure to conform to masculinity norms, encouraging adoption of counterhegemonic behaviors within engineering teams.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set clear expectations: Establish ground rules promoting respectful communication and appreciation of diverse perspectives. - Model inclusive behavior: Educators demonstrate emotional openness and collaborative practices. - Provide positive reinforcement: Acknowledge effective teamwork, empathy, and inclusive leadership during engineering projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model inclusive behaviors: TAs can exemplify emotional openness and collaboration, ensure inclusive team formations. - Practice active listening: TAs can validate students' feelings. - Intervene appropriately: TAs can address exclusionary behaviors. - Reinforce positive behaviors: TAs can acknowledge and praise effective teamwork and inclusivity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students feel more comfortable expressing emotions and engaging in collaborative practices. - A positive culture mitigates the persistence of hegemonic masculinities by reshaping norms around acceptable behaviors in engineering education.

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

Aspect	Recommendation	Link to masculinities and emotions in engineering education	Implementation strategies	Role of teaching assistants	Expected outcomes
5. Address Institutional Factors	Align assessment and reward structures with collaborative and inclusive practices rather than individual competition in engineering education.	Institutional emphasis on individual achievement reinforces hegemonic masculinities. Shifting focus to collaborations and teamwork skills encourages counterhegemonic practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design collaborative assessments: Include group projects that value collaboration and collective problem-solving. - Evaluate transversal skills: Incorporate criteria assessing collaboration, communication, and emotional reflexivity. - Provide faculty support: Offer training for educators on facilitating inclusive environments and addressing masculinities and emotions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback to faculty: TAs can communicate observations about classroom dynamics. - Assist in assessment: TAs can help evaluate collaborative and emotional intelligence skills. - Advocate for students: TAs can represent student concerns regarding team dynamics or classroom culture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students recognize the importance of collaborative skills in engineering. - Institutional support reinforces counterhegemonic practices, helping shift the engineering culture over time.
6. Encourage Peer Learning and Support Networks	Facilitate the formation of peer support groups where engineering students share experiences and strategies for effective teamwork.	Peer networks provide spaces to discuss challenges related to hegemonic masculinities and support adoption of counterhegemonic behaviors.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize peer mentoring programs: Pair students with mentors exemplifying inclusive practices and emotional intelligence. - Create discussion forums: Establish platforms for open discussions on team dynamics and strategies for collaboration. - Promote collaborative learning: Encourage study groups focusing on problem-solving and design thinking outside formal classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate peer networks: TAs can help organize and support peer mentoring programs. - Moderate discussion forums: TAs can oversee forums where students discuss teamwork and emotions. - Encourage collaborative learning: TAs can promote and participate in study groups and collaborative sessions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer support empowers students to challenge traditional norms and adopt inclusive behaviors. - Sharing experiences normalizes emotional expression and collaboration as valuable in the engineering learning process.

Abbreviation: TA, teaching Assistant.